

EFFECT OF PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ON YIELD, QUALITY, ECONOMICS AND SOIL PROPERTIES OF BITTER GOURD

Impana .M.N^{1*}, A. M. Sonkamble², A. P. Wagh³, S.O.Bawkar⁴ and D.S.Kankal⁵¹PG Student Department of Vegetable Science, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola 444104, Maharashtra (MS), India.²Professor and Head, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola – 444104, Maharashtra (MS), India.³Associate Professor, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola – 444104, Maharashtra (MS), India.⁴Associate Professor, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola – 444104, Maharashtra (MS), India.⁵Associate Professor, Department of Soil Science, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola – 444104, Maharashtra (MS), India.

impanamn46@gmail.com

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. PDKV, Akola to study the effect of plant growth regulators on growth, yield and quality of bitter gourd. The plant growth regulators brassinosteroid 1ppm, brassinosteroid 1.5ppm, 6-BA 60ppm, 6-BA 120ppm, TIBA 20 ppm, TIBA 40 ppm, GA₃ 25ppm, GA₃ 50 ppm and control are applied at an interval of 15, 30, 45 DAS. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design (RBD) with three replications. Result shows that application of GA₃ 50 ppm found most effective in increasing in the yield characters like number of fruits per vine, fruit weight, fruit yield per vine, fruit yield per plot and fruit yield per hectare. Quality parameters like fruit length, fruit diameter, and TSS also increased with the application of GA₃ 50ppm. BC ratio also found highest with the GA₃ 50ppm.

Key words : yield, economics, bitter gourd and plant growth regulators

Introduction

Bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia*) is an important vegetable crop which belongs to the family cucurbitaceae. Bitter gourd belongs to genus *momordica* which includes approximately fifty-nine species. This family contains many beneficial vegetables and bitter gourd is among them. Bitter gourd is a tropical plant that likes moist and warm areas. Bitter gourd is an annual and climbing plant and its delicate stem can be upto 1 to 2 m in length. The leaves are hand shaped, long-stalked and lobed and the lobes are elongated, oval shaped, toothed and pointed. The flowers are yellow and produce fruit in summer. The fruit, which looks like a lumpy shuttle, turns orange when ripe. The fruits are approximately 10 cm in width and 20 cm in length with flat and 20-30 seeds that turn brown as they mature (Yilmaz, S.S., 2023). Bitter gourd is a highly cross pollinated crop because flowering is a monoecious in nature. Insects, especially bees, pollinate the flowers. Pollination can be a problem during the wet season since bees are less active during overcast condition. The anthesis started from 4.A.M to 7:30 A.M and flowers become fully open from 6.00 A.M. to 9.55 A.M.

Plant growth regulators (also known as growth regulators or plant hormones) are chemicals used to alter the growth of a plant or plant part. Exogenous application of plant growth regulators can alter at 2 or 4 leaf stage which is critical stage for suppression or promotion of either sex (Desai *et al.*, 1994). Plant growth regulator for example brassinosteroid, 6BA, TIBA, and GA₃ etc. have been professed to play an energetic role in modifying the development and growth of many horticultural crops.

Among plant growth regulators, brassinosteroid occupies a significant place due to its capability to positively affect plant development and growth. It promotes cell expansion and cell division, and play a role in etiolation and production. 6 BA increases branching and enhance flowering in wide range of herbaceous and woody ornamentals, improving crop marketability. TIBA induce profuse flowering and fruiting with concomitant loss of apical dominance. GA₃ is an important growth regulator that may have many uses to modify the yield and yield contributing character of plant (Rafeekher *et al.*, 2002). Keeping in mind the above views, the present study was undertaken to study how foliar application of plant growth regulators sources affects the yield and quality of bitter gourd.

Materials And Methods

The experiment was carried out at the Instructional Farm, Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. PDKV, Akola during the *kharif* season of 2022. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design (RBD) with nine treatments *viz* brassinosteroid @ 1 ppm, brassinosteroid @ 1.5 ppm, 6-BA @ 60 ppm, 6-BA @ 120 ppm, TIBA @ 20ppm, TIBA @ 40 ppm, GA₃ @ 25 ppm, GA₃ @ 50 ppm, and

control with three replications. The plant growth regulators was sprayed at an interval of 15, 30 and 45 DAS.

The F₁ hybrid was used for the experiment. There were 27 plots measuring 1.5 m X 1 m. After land preparation FYM 25kg/ha and SSP 100 kg/ha was applied at planting. Urea was applied (200kg/ha) at 15 and 30 days after emergence. Murate of potash was applied after 15 and 30 days after emergence. Three seeds were placed in each pit and after sowing it was immediately covered with the loose soil and irrigation was provided. After emergence of seedlings allowed only two seedlings per pit for growth and development.

During research yield characters like number of fruits per vine, fruit weight, fruit yield per vine, fruit yield per plot and fruit yield per hectare was taken. Quality parameters like fruit length, fruit diameter and TSS was recorded. Soil status and BC ratio also recorded.

Results And Discussion

Effect of plant growth regulators on yield parameters

The present data revealed that treatment T₈ (GA₃ 50ppm) exhibited significantly highest fruits per vine (37.00) which was at par with T₇ (36.00), T₂ (34.00). Where as lowest number of fruits per vine found in T₉ (27.00). This is due to application of GA₃ suppresses the male flowers and promote the female flowers which results in a greater number of fruit set there by increasing the number of fruits. Similar findings found by Jishnu *et al.* (2023) in sponge gourd, and Vadigeri *et al.* (2001) in cucumber. The data regarding fruit weight presented in Table.No.1 observed that, foliar application of plant growth regulators has significant effect on weight of fruit. The foliar application of treatment T₈ (GA₃ 50ppm) exhibited significantly maximum fruit weight (147.33g). Whereas, minimum fruit weight was recorded in treatment T₉ (126.33g). During early stages of fruit development GA₃ directly or indirectly influences the cell number, size and density. The results are in agreement with the findings of Jishnu *et al.* (2023) in sponge gourd and Kadi *et al.* (2018) in cucumber.

The present investigation revealed that the treatment T₃ (GA₃ 50ppm) shows maximum fruit yield per vine (3.73kg) which was followed by treatment T₇ (3.37 kg), T₂ (3.20kg) Where as, minimum fruit yield per vine (2.50 kg) was recorded in treatment T₁₃ (control). An increase in fruit yield in treated plants may be attributed to the reason that plant remained physiologically more active to build up sufficient food stock for the developing flowers and fruits, ultimately leading to higher yield. Increased fruit yield is also due to the increase in pistillate flowers production and ultimately harvested more number of fruits per plant. These findings are in consonance with those of Kadi *et al.* (2018) in cucumber, and Shantappa *et al.* (2005) in bitter gourd. The result of fruit yield per plot showed significant difference among different treatments. The maximum fruit yield per plot (37.28kg) was recorded in T₈ (GA₃ 50 ppm) which was at par with

the treatment T₇ (36.00kg).. Where as the minimum fruit yield per plot (18.07kg) was recorded in T₉ (control). The increasing fruit yield per plot is GA₃ might be due to the consequence of GA₃ on cell elongation, stimulated RNA and protein synthesis and better diversion of food material towards fruit. Similar result found in Dalai *et al.* (2016) in cucumber.

The data related to findings of fruit yield per hectare as influenced by treatment T₈ (GA₃ 50 ppm) imparted maximum fruit yield per hectare (236.67 q) which was at par with the treatment T₇ (222.67q). While, minimum fruit yield per hectare (171.00q) was resulted in treatment T₉ (control). The probable reason for increased fruit yield by GA₃ treatment may be due to increased fruit set percent, fruit weight, length and diameter of fruits ultimately produced the highest yield. Similar result was found by Dalai *et al.* (2016) in cucumber.

Effect of plant growth regulators on quality parameters

The data represented significant difference among different treatments. The treatment T₈ (GA₃ 50ppm) exhibited significantly maximum fruit length (17.00cm) which was at par with the treatments T₇ (16.33), T₂ (15.53). Whereas, minimum fruit length was found in treatment T₉ (control) (10.77). This may be due to higher photosynthesis and respiration occurs in treated plants compared to control (water spray) by increasing accumulation of carbohydrates resulted in increasing weight and length of the fruit. The similar results are reported by Jishnu *et al.* (2023) in sponge gourd and Kadi *et al.* (2018) in cucumber. The investigation of data is found in Table No. 2 observed that foliar application of plant growth regulators represented significant effect on diameter. The fruit diameter significantly showed maximum diameter of fruit (4.83cm) was recorded in Treatment T₈ (GA₃ 50ppm) which was at par with T₇ (4.50cm), T₁ (4.03cm), T₂ (4.03cm), T₄ (3.63 cm). While minimum diameter of fruit was exhibited in treatment T₉ (3.03cm). This is due to function of fertilized ovule or the seed in relation to growth of the fruits is to synthesize hormones which initiate to maintain metabolic gradient along with the translocation of food towards fruits. Similar results found by Jishnu *et al.* (2023) in sponge gourd, and Sureshkumar *et al.* (2016) in bitter gourd.

The result of TSS showed significant difference among different treatments. The maximum TSS was recorded in T₈ (4.60) which is at par with the treatments T₇ (4.47), T₆ (4.21), T₁ (4.40), T₂ (4.57), and T₃ (4.13). Where minimum was recorded in the T₉ Control (3.87). The increase in T.S.S. of fruits seems probably due to accumulation of metabolites which stimulated functioning of a number of enzymes in physiological process, which turns, hydrolyzed starch and helped in the metabolic activity during the change of available starch into sugar and T.S.S. These results agree with the reports of Anayat *et al.* (2020) in bitter gourd

Effect of plant growth regulators on soil properties

Effect of plant growth regulators on available NPK

The data expressed in the table recorded that, available NPK in soil found to be statistically non-significant in the present investigation.

Effect of plant growth regulators on economics of bitter gourd

The maximum benefit cost ratio (3.12) was recorded with the treatment T₈ GA₃ at 50 ppm, whereas the minimum benefit cost ratio (2.24) was recorded with control treatments.

Conclusion

It is concluded that among application of different growth regulators, spraying of GA₃ at 50ppm gave maximum number of fruits per vine, fruit weight, fruit yield per vine, fruit yield per plot, fruit yield per hectare and quality parameters like fruit length, fruit diameter and TSS. It is also concluded that treatment GA₃ 50ppm has produced higher yields and good monetary returns.

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Table 1. Effect of plant growth regulators on yield parameters of bitter gourd

Treatments	Number of fruits per vine	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit yield per vine	Fruit yield per plot	Fruit yield per hectare (q/ha)
Brassinosteroid -1ppm	33.00	143.33	2.97	21.00	204.33
Brassinosteroid-1.5ppm	34.00	144.67	3.20	31.31	212.00
6-BA-60ppm	30.67	127.33	2.70	24.84	180.25
6-BA-120ppm	31.33	133.67	2.90	32.10	197.65
TIBA-20ppm	28.33	137.67	2.63	19.23	182.67
TIBA-40ppm	29.33	143.00	3.03	19.52	203.33
GA ₃ -25ppm	36.00	146.67	3.37	36.00	222.67
GA ₃ -50ppm	37.00	147.33	3.73	37.28	236.67
Control	27.00	126.33	2.50	18.07	171.00
F-test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(M)±	1.15	4.97	0.09	1.162	6.28
CD at 5%	3.47	14.91	0.27	3.48	18.83

Table 2. Effect of plant growth regulators on quality of bitter gourd

Treatments	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit diameter (cm)	TSS (%)
Brassinosteroid -1ppm	14.47	4.03	4.40
Brassinosteroid-1.5ppm	15.53	4.03	4.57
6-BA-60ppm	11.20	3.33	4.13
6-BA-120ppm	13.40	3.63	4.27
TIBA-20ppm	12.00	3.30	3.90
GA ₃ -25	16.33	4.50	4.47
GA ₃ -50ppm	17.00	4.83	4.60
Control	10.77	3.03	3.87
F-test	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(M)±	0.82	0.13	0.16
CD at 5%	2.48	0.39	0.48
CD at 5%	2.48	0.39	0.48

Table 3. Effect of plant growth regulators on available Nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium of bitter gourd

Treatments	Available Nitrogen(kg/ha)	Available phosphorous(kg/ha)	Available Potassium(kg/ha)
Brassinosteroid -1ppm	259.24	28.67	451.00
Brassinosteroid-1.5ppm	262.67	29.33	459.43
6-BA-60ppm	238.04	27.00	442.11
6-BA-120ppm	228.01	26.33	447.86
TIBA-20ppm	233.71	26.67	440.04
TIBA-40ppm	227.67	27.33	447.86
GA ₃ -25ppm	243.64	31.33	482.77
GA ₃ -50ppm	266.00	33.13	487.37
Control	226.00	26.00	438.00
F-test	NS	NS	NS
SE(M)±	14.61	2.13	14.61
CD at 5%	–	–	–

Table 4. Effect of plant growth regulators on economics of bitter

Treatments	Gross monetary return (Rs)	Cost of cultivation(RS)	Net returns (Rs)	B:C ratio
Brassinosteroid-1ppm	347361	122650	224711	2.83
Brassinosteroid-1.5ppm	360400	124650	235750	2.89
6-BA-60ppm	306425	124650	181775	2.45
6-BA-120ppm	324700	128650	196050	2.52
TIBA-20ppm	310539	125750	184789	2.46
TIBA-40ppm	345661	130850	214811	2.64
GA ₃ -25ppm	378539	123450	255089	3.06
GA ₃ -50ppm	402339	126250	276089	3.18
Control	290700	120650	170050	2.40